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Nestin can activate gene expression in cells.

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We demonstrate here that changes in expression of an intermediate filament protein are sufficient to result in significant remodeling of the cellular transcriptome. Nestin transduction activated expression of multiple homeotic transcription factors with oncogenic potential, including *BBX*, *BSX*, *PBX4* and *SOX3*. Nestin also engaged energy homeostasis resources in the cell through the protein synthesis machinery by activating *Rpl10l*.